

Article

Online Digital Tools for Expert Assisted Self-Evaluation of Environmental Impact: Benchmarking, Synthetic Data Generation and Advanced Analytics Based on Use Case Life Cycle Assessment

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Featured Application

The featured application developed in the current work is a digital toolkit for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data processing, which provides a set of online digital tools to facilitate access to, interpretation of, and benchmarking of LCA results obtained for use cases in the key sectors of fertilizer, textiles and packaging. The digital toolkit described in this work is available online (refer to Data Availability Statement).

Abstract

Background: This paper presents the development of digital tools created within the BIORADAR European project to improve user access to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) results from the project's use cases and to enable users to upload, benchmark and analyze their own data. The work addresses common challenges in circularity and environmental impact assessment, particularly data availability and expert-assisted self-assessment for users such as small- and medium-sized enterprises. **Methods:** The LCA data for the project use cases is calculated using the Environmental Footprint methodology. Benchmarking compares bio-approach use cases with traditional approaches across three key sectors selected by the BIORADAR project: fertilizer, textile and packaging. These sectors are recognized by the European Commission as three of the most important sectors in terms of environmental impact. Case impact factor data are normalized using a reference statistic, and a weighting is assigned to each key performance indicator to calculate the global score. Individual impact factor values can also be used for benchmarking. Synthetic data are generated through an advanced statistical decomposition algorithm. Advanced data analytics are provided with clustering and a decision tree algorithm using supervised machine learning. **Results:** Two examples of decision-oriented case studies are used to illustrate how the platform can support the interpretation and use of already computed LCA results in realistic settings. The web-based expert-assisted self-assessment tool, developed in JavaScript, allows users to input their data, benchmark them against project results and perform multidimensional data analysis. The resulting digital tools provide access to LCA data for each use case, generate realistic synthetic datasets preserving key statistical properties, support benchmarking of both project and user-uploaded cases, and perform data analytics, which complement the benchmarking module with a structural and exploratory interpretation of the data.

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Conclusions: Overall, the tools integrate use case benchmarking, data processing, advanced analytics and user interfaces to facilitate environmental self-assessment and comparison within the BIORADAR framework.

Keywords: online digital tools; benchmarking; data analytics; bio-based products; fertilizer; packaging and textile sectors; LCA data; expert-assisted self-assessment; use cases

1. Introduction

The broad context of the BIORADAR project [1] is to reduce the environmental impact of industrial processes and products, especially in the fertilizer, textile and packaging sectors, which have been identified as being among the industrial sectors that have the greatest environmental impact. This can only be achieved with the collaboration and commitment of the industries themselves. However, it can be difficult for them to technically identify which areas (impact factors) they should focus on and what they can do to reduce the impact while being economically and practically feasible to execute.

For this aim, the BIORADAR project has been developed a monitoring system for the environmental and social sustainability and circularity of industrial bio-based systems. A bio-based system covers all sectors that rely on biological resources, processes, and principles. The BIORADAR project envisions a comprehensive approach to exploring the connections between bio-based systems and their applications, circularity, environmental and social impacts. This consists of examining the four key phases of industrial bio-based systems: 'biological resource production', 'processes', 'transportation' and 'end-of-life for bio-based products'.

This is important in the context of the European Union's transition to a bioeconomy with more widespread use of bio-based products, services and systems. There is a need for (i) greater understanding, from a system perspective, of the environmental, economic, and social aspects of circular industrial bio-based systems and (ii) digital benchmarking and monitoring tools.

BIORADAR proposes a simple, objective, and quantitative Bio-based systems Transition Indicators (BTI) framework. Within this framework, the digital tools presented in this paper are intended to improve user access to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) results, facilitate comparison between use cases, and support the interpretation of environmental performance indicators. In this sense, the proposed toolkit should be understood as a complementary decision-support layer built on already calculated LCA results rather than as a substitute for LCA modeling itself. Its practical value is especially relevant in expert or expert-assisted contexts, in which companies, consultants, or technical sustainability staff need to benchmark product cases, identify relevant impact differences, and communicate the results more clearly. The BIORADAR framework includes AI-benchmarking and analytics platform, a flexible expert-assisted self-assessment tool, a regulatory tracker tool, and a multidimensional performance scorecard.

There are currently many circular economy projects being carried out under the European Green Deal and as part of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP). This is supported by legislation such as the Waste Framework Directive, the new Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) and the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR).

These projects usually provide, as part of the results, an environmental analysis based on the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for each use case considered. However, interpretation and visualization (graphs) of the obtained results are often done by LCA experts in spread-

sheets, typically to show and analyze the most important impact categories. This modus operandi presents a limitation for the broader understanding and practical use of LCA data for decision-making. The BIORADAR project was developed to address these issues by providing an integrated set of online web-based tools for accessing and evaluating results data.

According to [2], LCA software tools typically include a user interface for modeling the product system, a life cycle unit process database, an impact assessment database supporting different methodologies and a calculator combining data from the database with the product system modeling. However, these tools, even the widely used tools like Sphera LCA for Experts [3] and SimaPro [4], lack advanced analytics or the capacity to generate synthetic LCA datasets with interpretable classification outputs [2,5]. On the other hand, there are platforms like LCA Calculator [6], which are mainly focused on data simulation and uncertainty calculation, parameter estimation, and process modeling [7,8]. Hence, there is a lack of more user-oriented analytical environments that support comparison, interpretation, and exploratory pattern detection across sets of product cases. In this context, the BIORADAR toolkit aims to contribute a complementary layer that links standardized LCA results with benchmarking, synthetic data generation, and advanced analytics in a form oriented toward interpretation and decision-support.

To better position the contribution of the present work, it is useful to distinguish between conventional LCA modeling/calculation tools and post-LCA decision-support environments. Conventional LCA software and LCA calculators are mainly oriented toward inventory modeling, impact calculation, simulation or uncertainty analysis. By contrast, the BIORADAR toolkit is conceived as a broader post-LCA and multidimensional decision-support environment for bio-based systems. It integrates benchmarking, exploratory analytics, circularity-oriented interpretation, and regulatory intelligence based on already computed sustainability indicators. Table 1 shows what the BIORADAR toolkit offers compared to other options.

Recent literature references on ‘data benchmarking’ applied to Life Cycle Assessment include [9,10]. In [9], Greif et al. applied a knowledge graph-based framework to support sustainable decision-making by integrating, enriching, and analyzing heterogeneous data sources. On the other hand, Grajewski et al. [10] performed a detailed comparison of three digital tools for environmental product assessment: SimaPro, Sustainable Minds and GaBi. The strengths and weaknesses of each of the IT tools were identified. According to the authors, in terms of positive aspects, SimaPro was highlighted for complex models, Sustainable Minds for comparing different product variants to find optimal solutions, and Gabi for multilevel modeling. On the minus side, the authors considered that Sustainable Minds lacked detail in the presentation of results, while Gabi had limited database access.

Recent published developments in ‘data analytics’ applied to Life Cycle Assessment include [11,12]. In [11], Kolozis et al. discussed the application of machine learning (ML) tools to convert static LCA into dynamic analyses, enabling predictions for different scenarios and improving real-time decision-making. Furthermore, in [12], Chen et al. applied machine learning, specifically large language models trained on scientific papers, to mitigate data inaccuracies and missing inventory data, focused on evaluating the environmental impact of an industrial hydrogen production process.

Returning to the focus of the current work, the BIORADAR digital toolkit has five main modules: a use cases repository, benchmarking, advanced data analytics, a synthetic data generator and the expert-assisted self-assessment tool (Figure 1).

Table 1. Comparison between conventional LCA software/calculators and the BIORADAR toolkit.

	Conventional LCA Software/ LCA Calculators	BIORADAR Toolkit
Main purpose	LCA modeling, impact calculation, simulation, parameter estimation or uncertainty analysis	Post-LCA and multidimensional decision-support environment for bio-based systems
Main scope	Mainly environmental LCA	Environmental, economic, social and circularity assessment, plus regulatory intelligence
Type of input	Life cycle inventories, process models, parameters or LCA datasets	EF 3.1 impact indicators, company/use-case data, sustainability KPIs and sectoral reference cases
Main outputs	Environmental impact results, contribution analysis, reports or simulated scenarios	Benchmarking, hotspot-oriented interpretation, synthetic data, clustering, decision rules, scorecards and regulatory insights
Decision-support role	Supports expert environmental assessment	Supports comparison, communication, prioritization and improvement planning across sustainability dimensions
User profile	Mainly LCA experts or technical users	Expert or expert-assisted SMEs, sustainability teams, researchers and policymakers
Sector/application focus	Generic LCA modeling or product assessment	Bio-based systems, demonstrated in fertilizers, textiles, packaging and related bio-based value chains
Beyond environmental LCA	Usually limited or external to the core tool	Includes circularity, social and economic dimensions, SDG-oriented scorecard, and policy/regulatory tracker
Added value	Robust calculation and modeling environment	Integrated interpretation layer combining validated indicators, AI-supported analytics, benchmarking and regulatory intelligence

Figure 1. Overall schematic of the digital tools.

The purpose of this work is to present the design and implementation of the BIORADAR digital toolkit for LCA-based benchmarking, synthetic data generation, and exploratory analytics across selected bio-based sectors. Its significance lies in showing how already computed LCA results can be transformed into a more accessible and interpretable

decision-support environment. This is especially useful for expert or expert-assisted users who need to compare product cases, identify relevant impact differences, and explore patterns in limited or sensitive datasets. Recent works in data simulation for LCA have been limited to uncertainty calculation and parameter estimation [13–16], rather than forming part of a data analytics ‘pipeline’.

In summary, this paper demonstrates the technical design and proof-of-concept application of BIORADAR toolkit, which supports the comparison and interpretation of LCA results through benchmarking, synthetic data generation, and advanced analytics. The study shows that the proposed toolkit can provide a useful complementary decision-support layer for selected bio-based sectors. External validation is also an important component of the development and has included public demonstrations, end-user (SME) questionnaire surveys, user registration and expert feedback, among others. This is further detailed in the discussion part (Section 4) of the paper.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the materials and methods, including LCA analysis and data, benchmarking, synthetic data and advanced analytics. Section 3 presents the results (the digital tool implementation and user interface), including the expert-assisted self-assessment tool (benchmarking), data simulator and advanced data analytics (clustering with decision tree). The tool functionality is illustrated through the following two exemplary use cases: (i) benchmarking and comparison of a user use case using global score and individual impact factor comparison and (ii) synthetic data generation and its use for advanced data analytics to complement and augment the benchmarking, use case comparison, and evaluation. Section 4 provides a discussion, and Section 5 gives the conclusions.

2. Materials and Methods

In this section, the theoretical background and methodology applied in the digital tools are detailed. Firstly, the LCA analysis and data is explained (Section 2.1), followed by the benchmarking algorithm (Section 2.2), data simulation (Section 2.3), advanced analytics (Section 2.4) and design considerations (Section 2.5).

2.1. LCA Analysis and Data

LCA is a multi-criteria tool used to analyze and evaluate the environmental impacts linked to services or products. The tool takes into account the stages and processes across the complete life cycle. LCA is framed by the international standards [17–19].

The LCA was performed using the Environmental Footprint (EF) methodology (v3.1) and the Sphera LCA for Experts software (v10.7.1.28). The scope of the bio-based products studied was from ‘cradle-to-gate’ for those in the packaging and textile sectors; however, the use stage was also included for the fertilizer sector given its significant influence on overall environmental outcomes.

Rationale for selecting EF 3.1—The Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method was selected as the reference life cycle impact assessment method because it provides a harmonized European framework for assessing the environmental performance of products and organizations. This is particularly relevant for the BIORADAR project, which was developed in the context of European bio-based value chains and aims to support comparability across different sectors, including fertilizers, textiles and packaging. Moreover, the use of a common impact assessment method is essential. EF 3.1 provides a defined set of 16 environmental impact categories, together with normalization and weighting factors that can be used to calculate a composite global score and compare use cases in a transparent and reproducible way. Other life cycle impact assessment methods, such as ReCiPe and ILCD-based recommendations, are also scientifically robust and widely used in

LCA practice. ReCiPe provides midpoint and endpoint indicators and is useful for broader environmental interpretation, while ILCD offers detailed methodological guidance for LCA studies. However, EF 3.1 was prioritized in this study because it is more directly aligned with the European policy context, offers a harmonized structure for product environmental assessment, and provides the normalization and weighting framework required for the benchmarking logic implemented in BIORADAR. To clarify the methodological positioning of EF 3.1 in relation to other commonly used approaches, Table 2 summarizes the main differences among EF 3.1, ReCiPe and ILCD-based approaches.

Table 2. Comparison of EF 3.1 with other commonly used LCA impact assessment approaches: ReCiPe and ILCD.

Method	Main Orientation	Scope and Interpretability
EF 3.1	Harmonized European environmental footprint method for product and organization assessment	Provides a defined set of 16 environmental impact categories, with normalization and weighting factors that support comparability and aggregated scoring
ReCiPe	Life cycle impact assessment method with midpoint and endpoint indicators	Provides broad environmental interpretation through midpoint categories and damage-oriented endpoint indicators
ILCD-based approaches	European methodological guidance and recommended practice for LCA studies	Provides detailed guidance for conducting LCA and selecting impact assessment methods, with emphasis on consistency and methodological quality

Accordingly, the choice of EF 3.1 should be understood as a methodological harmonization decision. It ensures that all reference cases and user-uploaded cases can be compared using the same environmental impact categories, units, normalization factors and weighting structure. This is essential for the benchmarking, ranking and hotspot-oriented interpretation functions implemented in the BIORADAR toolkit.

The analyzed bio-based products for each sector was a representative set, whose selection can be found in the BIORADAR website [1,20]. Table 3 shows the assessed bio-based products.

Table 3. List of bio-based products analyzed in the BIORADAR project.

Sector	Product Category
Fertilizers	Algae, compost, Feather Meal, and Wood Vinegar
Packaging	Cardboard, composite, and paper
Textiles	Bio-based fiber, fossil-based fiber, man-made cellulosic fiber, natural plant fiber, and natural protein fiber

The functional unit was 1 kg of biowaste/residue or 1 m³ of wastewater treated for the fertilizer sector, and 1 kg of finished product for the packaging and textile sectors.

The analysis covered the 16 environmental impact categories included in the EF methodology. The results were normalized and weighted to support the identification of key impact drivers and hotspots [21,22]. The normalization and weighting factors are shown in Table 4. More information, including the inventories, will be available soon on the BIORADAR website.

Table 4. Normalization and weighting values for each impact factor considered in the EF 3.1 methodology.

Impact Categories	Unit	Normalization Factor	Weighting Factor [%]
Acidification	mol H ⁺ eq./person	5.56×10^1	6.20%
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq./person	7.55×10^3	21.06%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTU _e /person	5.67×10^4	1.92%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq./person	1.61×10^{00}	2.80%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq./person	1.95×10^1	2.96%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq./person	1.77×10^2	3.71%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTU _h /person	1.73×10^{-5}	2.13%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTU _h /person	1.29×10^{-4}	1.84%
Ionizing radiation	kBq U-235 eq./person	4.22×10^3	5.01%
Land use	pt/person	8.19×10^5	7.94%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq./person	5.23×10^{-2}	6.31%
Particulate matter	disease incidences/person	5.95×10^{-4}	8.96%
Photochemical O ₃ formation	kg NMVOC eq./person	4.09×10^1	4.78%
Resource depletion, fossils	MJ/person	6.50×10^4	8.32%
Resource depletion, M&M	kg Sb eq./person	6.36×10^{-2}	7.55%
Water use	m ³ water eq./person	1.15×10^4	8.51%

2.2. Benchmarking—Similarity Between Use Cases

The following subsection presents some specific aspects of the data processing related to benchmarking. Firstly, the normalization and weighting of LCA data values (Section 2.2.1), followed by the distance measure used to compare cases (Section 2.2.2).

2.2.1. Data Preprocessing—Normalization and Weighting of LCA Data Values

Table 4 shows the normalization and weighting values that are applied to the corresponding LCA impact factor values for the global score calculation. The weighting value gives relative importance to each impact factor, with respect to the other impact factors, where the sum of the importance weight for all impact factors is 100%. For example, with reference to Table 4, ‘climate change’ has the highest relative weighting of 21.06% and ‘human toxicity, non-cancer’ has the lowest relative weighting of 1.84%. On the other hand, the normalization factors try to estimate the impact of each human being on earth (global population used in the EF normalization factors: 6,895,889,018) [21]. It can be seen that ‘human toxicity, cancer’ has the lowest normalization factor of 1.73×10^{-5} , whereas land use has the highest normalization factor of 8.19×10^5 .

The sources of the normalization and weighting factors [21,22] are official European Commission reports that give guidelines and standardized values for the European Union. Readers are referred to these publications for further details regarding the calculation of the normalization and weighting factors. In addition, in Section 2.2.2 of this paper, a worked example of the calculation applied to a use case is given.

Refer to Appendix A, Table A1, for full details of the unit abbreviations given in Table 4 (column 2).

2.2.2. Benchmarking—Global Score vs. Individual Impact Factor Values

The benchmarking offers two approaches to compare use cases: (i) global score per use case and (ii) individual impact factor values for each use case.

The global score numerical value is used as a reference to rank all cases in descending order, with the lowest global score (indicating the case with the lowest environmental impact) at the top of the ranking. The user can then find the position of their use case in the ranking, as well as the use cases that are closest to it (immediately before and after in the ranking). The global score is calculated as a weighted sum of the 16 impact factors, which are normalized and weighted using the values shown in Table 4.

The user can also choose an individual impact factor, for example, acidification and then see the ranking of the cases for that impact factor. In this comparison, the acidification value used is the ‘raw’ value, without weighting or normalization. Again, the cases are ranked in ascending order of the given impact factor values, with the case with the lowest acidification ranked first.

The formula for the global score, gS , is as follows:

$$gS = \sum_{j=1}^n |((v_{ij} / n_i) \times w_i)| \tag{1}$$

where v_{ij} is the value of impact factor i for case j , n_i is the normalization value for impact factor i and w_i is the weighting value for impact factor i .

An example calculation follows for the Fertilizer-Algae-Castro 2023 use case. Table 5 shows the original data values, the values divided by the normalization factor, the values multiplied by the weighting factor and the total (2.01×10^{-7}) of the values in the rightmost column, which corresponds to gS . The absolute value is used in the global score calculation to avoid negative contributions canceling positive impacts when credits or avoided burdens appear in specific impact categories. -It has been verified that the score for the Fertilizer-Algae-Castro 2023 use case in the digital platform coincides with the value reported in Table 5 (2.01×10^{-7}).

Table 5. Example of calculation of the global score, applying the normalization and weighting factors to the impact factor values for the Fertilizer-Algae-Castro 2023 use case.

Impact Categories	Impact Factor Value	Normalized Value	Weighted Value
Acidification	5.26×10^{-6}	9.47×10^{-8}	5.87×10^{-9}
Climate change	0.00276	3.65×10^{-7}	7.70×10^{-8}
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	0.0194	3.42×10^{-7}	6.57×10^{-9}
Eutrophication, freshwater	9.65×10^{-7}	6.01×10^{-7}	1.68×10^{-8}
Eutrophication, marine	1.31×10^{-6}	6.70×10^{-8}	1.98×10^{-9}
Eutrophication, terrestrial	1.38×10^{-5}	7.81×10^{-8}	2.90×10^{-9}
Human toxicity, cancer	5.49×10^{-13}	3.18×10^{-8}	6.78×10^{-10}
Human toxicity, non-cancer	2.07×10^{-11}	1.61×10^{-7}	2.96×10^{-9}
Ionizing radiation	0.00112	2.65×10^{-7}	1.33×10^{-8}
Land use	0.0146	1.78×10^{-8}	1.41×10^{-9}
Ozone depletion	6.20×10^{-17}	1.18×10^{-15}	7.47×10^{-17}
Particulate matter	4.47×10^{-11}	7.51×10^{-8}	6.73×10^{-9}
Photochemical O3 formation	3.52×10^{-6}	8.61×10^{-8}	4.12×10^{-9}
Resource depletion, fossils	0.0457	7.03×10^{-7}	5.85×10^{-8}
Resource depletion, M&M	-3.87×10^{-10}	-6.08×10^{-9}	4.59×10^{-10}
Water use	0.000409	3.57×10^{-8}	3.03×10^{-9}
Total of Weighted Values:			2.01×10^{-7}

2.3. Data Simulation

The process used for data simulation in the current work requires information regarding the statistical properties of the data to be simulated. Typically, for each variable, this includes the mean value, standard deviation, maximum value and minimum value. In addition, a correlation matrix and/or covariance matrix is calculated for all variables to quantify the cross-correlations between them.

In the digital tool, the statistical information is obtained by allowing the user to select an existing sample data, which can be supplied by the user and/or taken from the digital platform use cases. The tool then calculates the statistics from this dataset. Then, the algorithm generates synthetic data using the statistics. The quality of the synthetic data is calculated as the closeness of match between the statistics of the real (chosen) data and the statistics of the (generated) synthetic data. This is performed in a loop for a number of iterations, after which the best set is chosen. The synthetic data generation process has a stochastic (random) component and can generate different data on each execution, even with the same statistical values. This is because it generates data within a range as a probability distribution, which typically forms a Gaussian or a “bell” curve.

In summary, the formula for simulation data generation is as follows:

$$Sim\ data = F (S, N, I) \quad (2)$$

where S represents the statistics of the real data sample, N is the number of samples required, and I is the number of iterations to be performed.

The following provides details of the quantified evaluation of the precision of the data simulator. The best simulation is selected from five runs using the % difference between the statistics of the seed data (mean, standard deviation, and cross-correlations) and the statistics of the simulated data. An example execution of the data simulator:

Simulation 1: Total score: 122.39 (Means: 4.95%, STD: 8.60%, Corrs: 108.84%);
 Simulation 2: Total score: 253.74 (Means: 18.94%, STD: 6.15%, Corrs: 228.64%);
 Simulation 3: Total score: 90.87 (Means: 3.34%, STD: 3.77%, Corrs: 83.75%);
 Simulation 4: Total score: 159.08 (Means: 11.08%, STD: 5.95%, Corrs: 142.04%);
 Simulation 5: Total score: 315.69 (Means: 45.32%, STD: 5.81%, Corrs: 264.57%).

In the above example, the simulator was executed five times (iterations), and simulation 3 was selected as the best one as it had the lowest “total score”, which represents the sum of the percentage differences between the means, standard deviations and correlations of the real (seed) data and those of the simulated data.

2.4. Advanced Data Analytics—Clustering Combined with a Decision Tree

Firstly, in the current work, it is stated that the AI used in the advanced data analytics consists of ‘machine learning’ algorithms, namely, unsupervised learning (clustering) and supervised learning (decision tree), which are linked as a data analytics pipeline. Note that the decision tree is used to interpret the clusters for the processed data, not as a predictive model for new data.

The K-means [23] clustering algorithm is a widely used unsupervised machine learning algorithm that groups a set of data records into clusters based on the similarity of the data points. The algorithm defines a number of centroids (or cluster centers) and iteratively assigns data points to the nearest centroid. It then recalculates the position of the centroids based on the assigned points. This is performed iteratively until a quality threshold is obtained (usually based on minimizing the intra-cluster distance and maximizing the inter-cluster distance).

In the current work, in addition to having information value in itself, clustering is used to supply the predictive labels (cluster IDs) for the decision tree algorithm [24]. This

is useful when pre-defined labeling does not exist for the data, which is the case in the present study. The process is depicted in Figure 2 for some fertilizer sector use cases (further explanation is given later in Section 3.2).

Figure 2. The cluster ID from the clustering provides the classifier label for training the decision tree.

The decision tree algorithm used in the current work (from Python scikit-learn V1.9.0) represents an optimized version of the classification and regression tree (CART) algorithm [24], a supervised machine learning algorithm frequently applied for classification of variables. It constructs a model with a tree-like structure composed of nodes and branches, where each node represents a decision rule based on a given threshold for specific attributes selected by the algorithm as representative of the phenomenon under study. The decision tree progressively splits the data into subsets based on the outcome of the previous decision rule (True/False), defining the branches of the tree-like structure. This process goes on until a terminal node (leaf) is reached, completing the classification (e.g., class = 1).

A key part of a decision tree induction algorithm is the “information gain measure”, which forms part of the basis of modern information theory, developed by Shannon [25] and applied to the construction of decision trees by Hunt [26]. In the context of partitioning

a training dataset, the heuristic has a key dependence on an information gain calculation to evaluate which attribute should be incorporated next and where it should be incorporated in the decision tree.

Let T be a set of training examples, each of the form $(x, y) = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_k, y)$, where $x_a \in \text{vals}(a)$ is the value of attribute a of example x , and y is the corresponding class label. The information gain IG for an attribute a is defined in terms of entropy H as follows:

$$IG(T, a) = H(T) - \sum_{v \in \text{vals}(a)} \frac{|\{x_a = v\}|}{|T|} \cdot H(\{x_a = v\}) \quad (3)$$

The mutual information is equal to the total entropy for an attribute if for each of the attribute values a unique classification can be made for the result attribute. In this case, the relative entropies subtracted from the total entropy are equal to zero.

In the current work, the clustering and decision tree techniques provide a machine learning capability for the evaluation of the LCA impact indicators for each group of use cases, helping to interpret and evaluate performance across different groupings.

The methodology uses a statistical decomposition technique to generate simulated data, combined with clustering and supervised learning to build a classifier model for benchmarking the cases, as explained in the following sections.

The following gives details of the decision tree parameters and processing. The dataset is split into train and test subsets, with 70% of the records allocated to the 'train' set and 30% to the 'test' set. The DecisionTreeClassifier function from the sklearn.tree Python library is used with criterion = "entropy" and max_depth = 3. The test inputs are used to predict the outputs. Accuracy is quantified using the sklearn.metrics.accuracy_score function by comparing the output tests with the output predictions.

Selection of the best decision tree model from five runs is based on classification performance of the decision tree. The following shows an example of the calculations performed at runtime:

```
[Model 1] Accuracy: 0.8000;
[Model 2] Accuracy: 0.6000;
[Model 3] Accuracy: 0.4000;
[Model 4] Accuracy: 0.6000;
[Model 5] Accuracy: 0.8000;
Best Accuracy: 0.8.
```

The decision tree with the highest accuracy (0.8) is chosen (model 1 or model 5).

2.5. General Design Considerations

When designing a digital tool, it is important to apply a methodology that guarantees the end result is adequate for the target end users. To guarantee this requirement, the AGILE approach with three simple but strategic steps was applied: (i) identify who the end users will be (profiles, skill levels, needs, etc.); (ii) identify what each end-user type wishes to do with the tool (type of queries, information retrieval and processing, functionality, etc.); and (iii) identify what information/data and functionality has to be in the tool to satisfy the end-user needs identified in step (ii).

The expert-assisted self-assessment tool requires the user to provide data/information (in principle, the 16 LCA key indicators) so that the benchmarking algorithm can compare the new user case with the ones in the system and provide a relative assessment to the user of their case. It is assumed that the user is able to provide LCA data for their case; hence, the user is either an LCA expert or has support from LCA experts (e.g., contracted consultants). The use cases are limited to the three sectors covered within the scope of the

BIORADAR project: textile, fertilizers and packaging, which have been chosen as three strategic sectors with respect to industrial environmental impact.

In practical terms, this means that the expert-assisted self-assessment tool is mainly intended for users who already have access to EF 3.1-compatible LCA results for their product system. Typical users therefore include LCA practitioners, consultants, technical sustainability staff, or company representatives working with internal or external expert support. The role of the tool is not to calculate the LCA itself, but to facilitate the structured comparison of the user case with the BIORADAR reference cases. In this way, the benchmarking module helps transform a multidimensional set of impact indicators into a more interpretable comparison, supporting the identification of hotspots, the evaluation of relative proximity to existing cases, and the discussion of possible improvement priorities. Therefore, the tool lowers the barrier to comparing and interpreting LCA outputs, although it does not eliminate the need for expert judgment in producing and validating the underlying data.

Different issues may occur (and have been mitigated) during user interaction: (i) the user has used a different tool (or *LCA calculator*) to generate the LCA data, and hence the data are not compatible; (ii) the user has data in different units and/or different impact categories, depending on the methodology used; (iii) the user has use cases that do not belong to one of the sectors covered in the BIORADAR project; and (iv) some of the impact factors are missing. For points (i) to (iii), the tool obliges the user to reformulate their data and provide them in a compatible form. For point (iv), the system can generate values for the missing impact categories based on the average values for the corresponding sector (e.g., fertilizer).

3. Results

The overall result of the work is the implementation of an integrated set of digital tools for end users of circularity and environmental impact evaluation. In this section, key innovative components of three of the digital tools are showcased: the self-assessment tool for benchmarking comparison, data simulation and advanced data analytics. This is done through two of decision-oriented case studies, whose purpose is to show how the platform can support the interpretation and use of already computed LCA results in realistic settings. Accordingly, BIORADAR was conceived as a decision-support layer built on standardized environmental impact indicators rather than as a substitute for LCA modeling.

The following two user case studies are detailed: in Section 3.1, expert-assisted SME (small- and medium-sized enterprise) benchmarking, and in Section 3.2, synthetic data-enabled exploratory analysis. These two cases show that the BIORADAR tool provides, on the one hand, direct support for comparing and interpreting already computed LCA results and, on the other hand, an optional advanced module for expert users who need to explore patterns in sparse or sensitive sustainability datasets. For each use case, the decision context is given first, followed by the type of input, main outputs, interpretation, and practical implications.

3.1. Expert-Assisted SME Benchmarking

Decision context: This first case focuses on an expert-assisted SME benchmarking use, where a company or consultant uploads the 16 EF 3.1 impact indicators of a product and uses the toolkit to identify the most comparable reference case, understand which impact categories drive the similarity or difference, and translate a complex LCA result table into a practical benchmarking insight for product positioning or improvement planning. This is summarized schematically in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Overall schematic of use case 1—expert-assisted SME benchmarking.

Type of input: Figure 4 shows, in the foreground, the users .csv /Excel file containing the 16 LCA impact factors for the user’s use case. In the background, the platform file repository screen can be seen, in which the user has used the ‘upload files’ option to upload the Excel file to the platform. Note that the user has uploaded the file indicating that it corresponds to the “fertilizer” sector.

Figure 4. User uploads data of their use case (my-use-case-AW).

To illustrate the difference between overall weighted benchmarking and category-level comparison, an illustrative user case (my-use-case-AW) was constructed from fertilizer sector reference profiles. More specifically, six impact factors were defined with values close (within 10%) to the BIORADAR fertilizer use case “Algae/Castro 2023”, while the remaining ten impact factors were defined with values close (within 10%) to “Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1”. As the global similarity is calculated using weighting factors, the six impact factors corresponding to “Algae/Castro 2023” account for 62.34% of the total weight, whereas the ten impact factors corresponding to “Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1” account for 37.66% of the total weight. Therefore, in terms of the global score, “Algae/Castro 2023” is the closest to the user use case, whereas “Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1” is more similar for a greater number of individual impact factors. Refer to Table 4 for further details of the weighting and normalization values.

Table 6 shows the example user use case (my-use-case-AW), the weightings and the BIORADAR cases from which ‘my-use-case-AW’ was derived.

Table 6. User use case defined from the top six impact factors by weight from “Algae/Castro 2023” and the remaining ten impact factors from “Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1”.

Impact Categories	WEIGHT (%)—Top 6 Impact Factors	WEIGHT (%)—Impact Factors 7–16	Algae/Castro 2023	Wood Vinegar/Product Valorization of Case 1	My-Use-Case-AW
Acidification		6.20%	5.26×10^{-6}	4.37×10^{-4}	4.37×10^{-4}
Climate change	21.06%		2.76×10^{-3}	1.94×10^{-1}	2.72×10^{-3}
Ecotoxicity, freshwater		1.92%	1.94×10^{-2}	-1.60×10^{00}	-1.69×10^{00}
Eutrophication, freshwater		2.80%	9.65×10^{-7}	6.30×10^{-7}	5.84×10^{-7}
Eutrophication, marine		2.96%	1.31×10^{-6}	1.65×10^{-4}	1.60×10^{-4}
Eutrophication, terrestrial		3.71%	1.38×10^{-5}	1.76×10^{-3}	1.80×10^{-3}
Human toxicity, cancer		2.13%	5.49×10^{-13}	-6.99×10^{-12}	-6.95×10^{-12}
Human toxicity, non-cancer		1.84%	2.07×10^{-11}	-8.63×10^{-10}	-8.29×10^{-10}
Ionizing radiation		5.01%	1.12×10^{-3}	1.16×10^{-1}	1.22×10^{-1}
Land use	7.94%		1.46×10^{-2}	1.06×10^{00}	1.57×10^{-2}
Ozone depletion		6.31%	6.20×10^{-17}	-3.56×10^{-13}	-3.59×10^{-13}
Particulate matter	8.96%		4.47×10^{-11}	2.86×10^{-9}	4.44×10^{-11}
Photochemical O3 formation		4.78%	3.52×10^{-6}	1.67×10^{-4}	1.76×10^{-4}
Resource depletion, fossils	8.32%		4.57×10^{-2}	-5.05×10^{-1}	4.52×10^{-2}
Resource depletion, M&M	7.55%		-3.87×10^{-10}	-6.06×10^{-7}	-3.61×10^{-10}
Water use	8.51%		4.09×10^{-4}	1.90×10^{-1}	3.82×10^{-4}
Total	62.34%	37.66%			

Once the user use case has been prepared and uploaded to the digital platform, the user can proceed to the “self-assessment tool”, in which s/he chooses the option “analyze with platform use cases and some of your files”. The user then selects all fertilizer sector cases (Algae, Compost, Feather Meal, and Wood Vinegar). Next, the user clicks “select files”, selects their file and then clicks the “benchmarking” option.

Main outputs: The benchmarking output is shown in Figures 5 and 6. Figure 5 presents the overall ranking of the fertilizer reference cases together with ‘my-use-case-AW’ based on the global weighted score. In this comparison, ‘my-use-case-AW’ ranked fourth among the 17 fertilizer cases, with ‘Algae/Castro 2023’ being its closest overall reference case. On the other hand, Figure 6 shows the category-level comparison for an individual impact factor

(acidification), where the closest reference case is ‘Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1’.

Figure 5. Benchmarking screen showing the ranking list of fertilizer sector use cases and the user use case AW for all 16 LCA impact factors.

Figure 6. Benchmarking screen showing the ranking list of use cases for individual LCA impact factors (acidification is shown).

Interpretation and practical implications: From the benchmarking results, it can be seen that the closest/most similar overall case to ‘my-use-case-AW’ is ‘Algae/Castro 2023’, whereas the closest/most similar case in terms of the number of matching individual impact factors is ‘Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1’ (eight matches). As explained previously, this is due to the weighting of the impact factors, which favors ‘Algae/Castro 2023’ in the overall comparison, whereas ‘Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1’ is closer to ‘my-use-case-AW’ for a greater number of individual impact factors (without weighting).

This example shows that the closest overall benchmark and the closest category-level matches do not necessarily coincide. The first reflects similarity across the full weighted EF profile, whereas the latter highlights specific impact categories in which the user case is closer to particular reference cases. In this sense, the two outputs answer different but complementary questions: which reference case is closest overall, and which cases are closest for the impact categories that matter most in the interpretation of the environmental profile.

Table 7 summarizes the rankings of the user use case ‘my-use-case-AW’ vs. the BIORADAR fertilizer use cases.

Table 7. Global (overall) score and rankings by impact factor: ranking of the user use case vs. BIORADAR use cases.

Impact Categories	Ranking		Closest Case
Overall score	4	Algae	Castro 2023
Acidification	6	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Climate change	2	Algae	Castro 2023
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	2	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Eutrophication, freshwater	2	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Eutrophication, marine	6	Wood Vinegar	Generic wood biomass (unspecified)
Eutrophication, terrestrial	9	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Human toxicity, cancer	3	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Human toxicity, non-cancer	3	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Ionizing radiation	15	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Land use	2	Algae	Castro 2023
Ozone depletion	4	Wood Vinegar	Product valorization of case 1
Particulate matter	1	Algae	Castro 2023
Photochemical O ₃ formation	6	Feather Meal	Case 3: unspecified animal's feather
Resource depletion, fossils	5	Algae	Castro 2023
Resource depletion, M&M	9	Algae	Castro 2023
Water use	5	Algae	Castro 2023

In the present example, the strongest relative ranking positions are observed for particulate matter (1), climate change (2), ecotoxicity freshwater (2), eutrophication freshwater (2), and land use (2), whereas weaker relative ranking positions are observed for ionizing radiation (15), eutrophication terrestrial (9), and resource depletion of M&M (9).

These results support two complementary interpretations. Firstly, in terms of comparative positioning, 'my-use-case-AW' was most closely aligned with 'Algae/Castro 2023' (overall weighted benchmark) and 'Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1' (category-level proximity for several individual impact factors). This helps position the user case relative to the fertilizer reference set included in BIORADAR.

Secondly, in terms of planning to reduce environmental impact, the focus may be regarded as priority categories for further investigation on 'ionizing radiation', 'eutrophication terrestrial' and 'resource depletion M&M', since they show the weakest relative positions in the current benchmark. Final prioritization should therefore consider both the category-level ranking and the relative importance of each impact category in the overall

weighted score. Addressing these categories could potentially improve the relative ranking of ‘my-use-case-AW’ with respect to other fertilizer products with similar impact profiles.

From a practical decision-support perspective, these results illustrate how the toolkit can support the first steps of environmental improvement planning. The platform does not directly prescribe process modifications, since this would require detailed inventory data, site-specific operational information and expert judgment. Instead, it helps identify which reference cases and impact categories deserve closer review. In the illustrative fertilizer case, the weaker relative positions observed for ionizing radiation, terrestrial eutrophication and resource depletion of minerals and metals would point the user toward a more detailed assessment of upstream energy-related contributions, nutrient-emission or use stage assumptions, and material or auxiliary input contributions, respectively.

Therefore, the practical value of the benchmarking output lies in structuring expert interpretation and supporting more focused environmental decision-making. It helps position a product case against comparable bio-based alternatives, highlights the impact categories where the case performs relatively worse than the reference set, and encourages a combined reading of the global weighted ranking and the individual category rankings. This avoids overreliance on a single aggregated score and supports a more transparent discussion of possible emission-reduction or product-improvement pathways, without replacing detailed LCA diagnosis or the technical design of process improvements.

3.2. Synthetic-Data-Enabled Exploratory Analysis

Decision context: The second case illustrates the role of synthetic data-enabled exploratory analysis, showing how, in situations with limited observations or confidentiality constraints, the toolkit can be used to generate privacy-preserving or data-sparse analytical scenarios that support pattern exploration, clustering, and interpretable comparison without claiming to replace full empirical validation. This is summarized schematically in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Overall schematic of use case 2—synthetic data-enabled exploratory analysis.

Type of input: A total of 16 LCA impact factors in EF 3.1 format for the following use cases. First, as shown in Figure 8, the user chooses a subset of platform use cases of interest. We have chosen the BIORADAR fertilizer use cases (algae, Wood Vinegar, and Feather Meal) to have a range across the score rankings discussed previously in Section 3.1, from

the best performers (lowest global environmental impact) to the worst performers (highest global environmental impact). Hence, the data inputs for this example are:

- Relevant BIORADAR fertilizer use cases (algae, Wood Vinegar, and Feather Meal);
- User case 'my-use-case-AW' described previously in Section 3.1;
- Synthetic dataset.

Figure 8. Selection of cases for synthetic data generation.

Main outputs: Synthetic data in Excel file containing 1000 cases of 16 LCA impact factors, together with clustering and decision tree outputs. The user processes the use cases to generate synthetic data, which produces an Excel file with data in the local computer. The user then uploads this file to the platform. Next, the user selects the synthetic data file to generate clustering and decision tree outputs (Figures 9–11).

Figure 9. Synthetic data are uploaded.

Figure 10. The user generates clusters from the synthetic data.

Figure 11. The user generates a decision tree from the synthetic data.

Interpretation and practical implications: Three clusters are clearly visible, indicated by green, red and dark blue symbols (Figure 10), which suggests the presence of three main groups within the selected fertilizers. The decision tree generated from the synthetic data and clustering results (Figure 11) classifies the data based on the cluster IDs and has four levels with the leaf (classifier) nodes located at the lowest level. Nodes that classify cluster 1 cases are dark blue, nodes that classify cluster 0 cases are red and nodes that classify cluster 2 cases are green. The most general criteria (threshold rules) are located higher in the tree, whereas the more specific criteria are lower down. For example, the top node threshold is “Ecotoxicity freshwater ≤ 3.869 ”. If this is true, the flow follows down to the left and reaches the next node “Resource Use Fossil ≤ 1.051 ”. If this is false, the flow follows down to the right and reaches the next node “Ecotoxicity freshwater ≤ 0.057 ”. Finally, if this is true, the flow goes down to the left and reaches the blue classifier node “Cluster = 0”.

Hence, a rule can be defined for cluster 0 use cases:

“Ecotoxicity freshwater ≤ 3.869 ” = true

“Resource Use Fossil ≤ 1.051 ” = false

“Ecotoxicity freshwater ≤ 0.057 ” = true

which can be rewritten as:

IF “Ecotoxicity freshwater ≤ 3.869 ” AND “Resource Use Fossil ≤ 1.051 ” AND “Ecotoxicity freshwater ≤ 0.057 ” THEN “cluster = 0”

The most important impact factors chosen by the decision tree to classify the cases are “ecotoxicity freshwater”, “resource use fossil”, and “ozone depletion”. The ranges and thresholds give quantitative rules for classifying the user use case.

From Figures 4 and 11, it can be seen that for the user use case ‘my-use-case-AW’, “ecotoxicity freshwater” = -1.69 , “resource use fossil” = 0.0452 and “ozone depletion” = -3.59×10^{-13} . Therefore, this case is classified by the decision tree as cluster 0 (from the top node, it first moves down to the left, then again to the left, and finally down to the left once more). It is now possible to study the other cases in cluster 0 to evaluate their impact factor profiles and statistics (ranges, max, and min for each impact factor).

Likewise, for the BIORADAR fertilizer use cases considered in Section 3.1 (‘Algae/Castro 2023’ and ‘Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1’), which were most similar to ‘my-use-case-AW’, both were also assigned to cluster 0, which is expected due to their similarity. The cluster assignment for each case and the corresponding decision tree navigation is detailed in Table 8.

Furthermore, Table 8 shows the following cluster assignments: ‘Feather Meal/Case 3: Unspecified’ was assigned to cluster 2, whereas ‘Algae/Life Project’, ‘Algae Arashiro 2018’, ‘Feather Meal/layer chicken feather’ and ‘Feather Meal/goose feather’ were assigned to cluster 1.

Table 8. Use case classification using clustering and the decision tree.

Use Case	Impact Factor Values			Decision Tree Navigation	Cluster Assigned
	Ecotoxicity Freshwater	Resource Use Fossil	Ozone Depletion		
my-use-case-AW	−1.69	0.0452	-3.59×10^{-13}	true, left true, left true, left	c = 0
Algae/Castro 2023	0.0194	0.0457	6.20×10^{-17}	true, left true, left true, left	c = 0
Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1	−1.6	−0.505	-3.56×10^{-13}	true, left true, left true, left	c = 0
Feather Meal/ Case 3: Unspecified	3.41	3.73	1.65×10^{-12}	true, left false, right false, right	c = 2
Algae/Life Project	3.9	8	4.28×10^{-15}	false, right false, right false, right	c = 1
Algae Arashiro 2018	8.27	7.1	7.94×10^{-16}	false, right false, right false, right	c = 1
Feather Meal/layer chicken feather	7.32	6.66	2.12×10^{-12}	false, right false, right false, right	c = 1
Feather Meal/ goose feather	7.39	8.14	2.12×10^{-12}	false, right false, right false, right	c = 1

The following observations can be made for ‘my-use-case-AW’: the values for ‘Ecotoxicity freshwater’, ‘Resource use fossil’ and ‘Ozone depletion’ values seem to be relatively low, which is favorable as they are key impact factors chosen by the decision tree algorithm to discriminate between cases. This is similar to the situation observed for the other use cases assigned to cluster 0, which tend to have low environmental impact profiles.

On the other hand, clusters 1 and 2 appear to have use cases with significantly higher impact values for ‘Ecotoxicity freshwater’, ‘Resource use fossil’ and ‘Ozone depletion’.

Compared with the benchmarking module presented in Section 3.1, this second analytical stage provides a different type of insight. While benchmarking shows where the user case stands relative to the available reference cases, the synthetic data-enabled exploratory analysis helps reveal the broader similarity structure of the selected dataset and identify which impact categories most strongly differentiate the resulting groups. In the present example, the clustering placed ‘my-use-case-AW’ together with ‘Algae/Castro 2023’ and ‘Wood Vinegar/Product valorization of case 1’, while the decision tree indicated that ‘ecotoxicity freshwater’, ‘resource use fossil’, and ‘ozone depletion’ were the most informative variables for distinguishing cluster membership. In this sense, the example described in Section 3.2 does not replace benchmarking but complements it by moving from relative ranking to profile-based interpretation.

4. Discussion

Proof-of-concept-validation: From a validation perspective, it is important to distinguish between internal (technical and expert user validation inside the project) and external (end users, stakeholders and experts outside the project).

In terms of internal validation, the synthetic data module was assessed through the statistical similarity between real and generated data, clustering through typical cluster optimization (elbow method, intra- and inter-cluster distances) and decision tree through the % of successful classifications of the use cases based on the cluster ID. The benchmarking module was validated by revising the internal consistency of the ranking results across the project use cases. In addition, the software was tested hands-on by project partners and revised according to their feedback during development. These elements support the technical feasibility and internal coherence of the proposed toolkit. It should be noted that the BIORADAR project includes two LCA data expert partners (CETENMA and NTT), who evaluated and advised on the development of the digital tools and provided the initial sets of use cases and data.

The LCA and other data uploaded as example use cases in the platform for the three key sectors (fertilizers, textiles, and packaging) were processed by experts (NTT/CETENMA) precisely to guarantee a high-quality base of use cases in the platform.

Any further data uploaded by users are validated to conform to the LCA EF3.0 format, namely 16 impact factors with the correct heading labels and a numeric value for each impact factor. If a value is missing, it is assigned the average value of the platform's default use cases for the corresponding sector. It is possible that the numerical value assigned to an impact factor is very different from the expected value for that impact factor (e.g., acidification); however, this is difficult to assert a priori as values can vary a lot from one use case to another. For example, the acidification value for the use case "Fertilizer-Algae-Arashiro 2018" is 0.0221, whereas for "Fertilizer-Algae-Castro 2023" it is 5.26×10^{-6} , and both values are valid. Hence, checking would need manual verification by a human moderator.

In terms of external validation, external user feedback was recently obtained through a detailed questionnaire survey involving 100 SMEs. The feedback was generally very positive and also provided useful information for making adjustments to the user experience. In addition, the BIORADAR project organized a major public event [27] that was open to external stakeholders, SMEs, experts and European Commission representatives. From this event, we received valuable positive feedback, and we now have over 50 registered users after being open to public registration for several months. As is habitual for any end-user digital platform launch, the user base is expected to grow over time, and further feedback received will allow it to evolve in response to user needs in the future.

Stability, sensitivity and uncertainty considerations: The LCA results used in the BIORADAR toolkit were generated using an established methodology, Environmental Footprint method v3.1, specific life cycle inventory databases and dedicated LCA software. Therefore, the platform does not introduce uncertainty associated with recalculating the LCA models themselves. Instead, the main stability and sensitivity considerations relate to the interpretation and benchmarking layer built on top of these already computed results. Likewise, uncertainty 'inherited' from LCA datasets, emission factors, and inventories is usually not disclosed by software developers (e.g., Sphera and PPro Sustainability), which prevents the authors from conducting further error propagation calculations. In any case, it is relevant to note that LCA results should be taken as estimates of the order of magnitude rather than as exact numeric results.

First, comparability depends on methodological consistency among the cases included in the platform. Since the benchmarking module compares EF 3.1-compatible impact

indicators, user-uploaded cases should be based on the same impact assessment method, compatible units and comparable system boundaries. If a user uploads data derived from different modeling assumptions, incomplete inventories or non-harmonized methods, the resulting comparison should be interpreted with caution and preferably reviewed by an LCA expert.

Second, the global score is sensitive to the normalization and weighting factors used to aggregate the 16 EF impact categories. These factors are standard EF values and are applied consistently across all cases; however, as with any aggregated environmental score, changes in weighting assumptions could affect the relative ranking of cases, particularly when cases have similar global scores. To reduce overreliance on a single aggregated metric, the toolkit reports both the global weighted ranking and the individual impact category rankings. This allows users to identify whether the same interpretation is supported at the category level and helps maintain transparency in hotspot-oriented interpretation.

Third, the synthetic data and machine learning outputs should be interpreted as exploratory rather than predictive. The synthetic data generator includes a stochastic component, so repeated runs may generate different datasets with similar statistical properties. For this reason, the quality of the generated data is assessed by comparing its statistical properties with those of the seed data, including mean values, standard deviations and correlations. Similarly, the decision tree is used to interpret the clusters obtained from the selected dataset, not to predict the future environmental performance of new products.

Overall, the current study addresses stability and uncertainty by using harmonized EF 3.1-based LCA results, applying the same normalization and weighting procedure to all cases, reporting both aggregated and disaggregated benchmarking outputs, and treating the synthetic data-enabled analytics as an exploratory layer. More systematic sensitivity analysis, alternative weighting scenarios and external validation with independent user cases remain relevant areas for future work.

Findings and implications: An important issue, as with any digital tool or application, is that the design, user interface and functionality should be appropriate for the types of users for whom the system is intended. The BIORADAR toolkit is designed for expert-assisted contexts rather than as a fully stand-alone tool for non-specialist users. This is because the workflow requires access to compatible LCA results, methodological consistency across the impact indicators, and informed interpretation of the benchmarking outputs. In practice, a company production manager or decision-maker may use the platform to compare a product case with the available reference cases and visualize the relative position of that case; however, the preparation, harmonization, and validation of the underlying LCA results would normally still require internal expertise or external consultancy support. Therefore, the main practical contribution of the toolkit is not to remove all technical barriers associated with LCA, but to facilitate the interpretation, comparison and communication of already computed results. A current applicability condition of the benchmarking module is that user cases need to fall within one of the BIORADAR sectors (fertilizer, textile or packaging) to be meaningfully compared with the project data. As commented, these are three of the most important sectors identified by the European Commission in relation to environmental impact.

In terms of technical validation, as mentioned, the synthetic data module and benchmarking module were internally tested under different scenarios, and the data analytics component was validated by cross-checking the assignment of use cases to clusters and the decision tree rules defined for the corresponding clusters. It should be noted that the decision tree is used to describe the clusters, not as a predictive model for new data.

In terms of end-user validation, as mentioned, the platform was first tested by project partners (especially those with LCA data expertise) and revised according to their feedback

during development. This was followed by a public conference presentation in Milan with key stakeholders and experts, as well as public online availability of the platform for registration. At present, we have over 50 registered users. As part of the validation activities, a structured questionnaire was sent to potential users. It was organized around seven dimensions—usability, fitness for purpose, credibility, usefulness, transferability, overall value and practical application—plus an open feedback section. Most items used a scale ranging from 1 to 5 (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). As an overall summary of the feedback, all evaluated dimensions exceeded a value of 4 out of 5, falling within a narrow range between 4.37 and 4.66. This indicates a consistently high level of satisfaction across the platform.

An added value of the advanced analytics module is that it complements benchmarking with a different level of interpretation. The benchmarking module provides a relative assessment of the user case, both through the overall weighted score and through the ranking of individual impact categories. By contrast, the synthetic data, clustering, and decision tree pipeline supports a more structural and exploratory reading of the data. It helps identify groups of environmentally similar cases, reveals which impact categories are most informative for separating those groups, and provides interpretable decision rules for understanding cluster membership.

This is particularly useful in small-data contexts, where the limited number of observed cases may constrain direct comparison. Accordingly, the second section of the toolkit should be understood not as a replacement for benchmarking, but as a complementary exploratory layer that helps interpret multivariate patterns and possible improvement pathways more clearly. At the same time, these outputs remain exploratory and proof-of-concept in nature and should not be interpreted as predictive evidence of future environmental performance or as a substitute for empirical validation.

Future research: With reference to the data simulation, the distribution of the simulated variables follows a Gaussian form, which is typical of methods similar to Monte Carlo. In general, this is an adequate approach; however, if some of the real variables have a non-Gaussian distribution (for example, a bias skewed to the left or right), it would be desirable for the simulated data to account for this characteristic. This aspect will be considered in future work. In addition, the normalization and weighting values applied to calculate the global score are currently built into the application and cannot be changed (they are standard values widely used in the literature). A future version could allow user to upload a file with customized values, especially for the weightings.

The BIORADAR use case repository will progressively increase as users upload more of their own data into the system. As new data accumulate in the platform, further data analytics and functionalities will be evaluated for leverage in future work. The sectors selected by the BIORADAR project (fertilizer, textile and packaging) are recognized by the European Commission as three of the most important and largest sectors in terms of environmental impact. Before adding new sectors, we will first work towards achieving impact in these three key sectors. As part of the BIORADAR project, a business case for scale-up and ‘circularity as a service’, among other concepts, was developed with a focus on the chosen sectors.

5. Conclusions

The paper presented the development of a digital toolkit for LCA data processing as part of the BIORADAR project. The main contribution of the present work is a useful set of online digital tools that facilitate access to, interpretation of, and benchmarking of LCA results obtained for use cases in the fertilizer, textile and packaging sectors. In this sense, the toolkit is best understood as a complementary decision-support layer rather

than as a replacement for conventional LCA software or expert practice. Two examples of decision-oriented case studies were used to illustrate how the platform can support the interpretation and use of already computed LCA results in realistic settings. The most immediate practical value lies in helping users compare cases, identify the impact categories driving the main differences, and communicate multidimensional environmental results in a more structured way. At the same time, the study shows that the platform is most appropriate for expert or expert-assisted use, since the production, harmonization and validation of the underlying LCA data still require technical expertise. The current work therefore demonstrates the technical feasibility and internal consistency of the BIORADAR toolkit, while broader external validation of its usability and decision-support impact will be performed in the following dissemination stage. The synthetic data and advanced analytics modules extend the exploratory capabilities of the platform, but their practical relevance depends on the user context and should therefore be regarded as complementary functionalities rather than universally necessary ones.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BTI	Bio-Based Systems Transition Indicators
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
EF	Environmental Footprint

ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
ML	Machine Learning
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
SME	Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprise

Appendix A

The following Table A1 provides a description of each unit abbreviations given in Table 4 (column 2) for the units of each LCA data impact factor, following the EC official guidelines detailed in [28].

Table A1. LCA data impact category unit descriptions [28].

Impact Category	Unit	Description
Acidification	mol H+ eq.	Moles of H+ equivalent per person. The potential impact of substances contributing to acidification is converted to the equivalent of moles of hydron (general name for a cationic form of atomic hydrogen, mol H+ eq).
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq.	The global warming potential of all GHG emissions is measured in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent (kg CO ₂ eq), namely all GHG are compared to the amount of the global warming potential of 1 kg of CO ₂ .
Ecotoxicity	CTUe	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems, normalized or measured on a per capita basis (impacts on freshwater ecosystems per person).
Eutrophication (freshwater)	kg P eq.	Eutrophication in ecosystems happens when substances containing nitrogen (N) or phosphorus (P) are released to the ecosystem. The potential impact of substances contributing to freshwater eutrophication is converted to the equivalent of kilograms of phosphorus (kg P eq).
Eutrophication (marine)	kg N eq.	Eutrophication in ecosystems happens when substances containing nitrogen (N) or phosphorus (P) are released to the ecosystem. The potential impact of substances contributing to marine eutrophication is converted to the equivalent of kilograms of nitrogen (kg N eq).
Eutrophication (terrestrial)	mol N eq.	Eutrophication arises when substances containing nitrogen (N) or phosphorus (P) are released to ecosystems. The potential impact of substances contributing to terrestrial eutrophication is converted to the equivalent of moles of nitrogen (mol N eq).
Human toxicity (cancer and non-cancer)	CTUh	This indicator refers to potential impacts, via the environment, on human health caused by absorbing substances from the air, water and soil. Direct effects of products on human health are currently not measured. The unit of measurement is Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh).
Ionizing radiation	kBq U-235 eq.	Kilo-Becquerel Uranium-235 equivalent per person, is a standard life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) metric used to measure the ionizing radiation (IR) potential of a product, service, or consumption pattern. It evaluates the potential damage to human health and ecosystems caused by the emission of radionuclides (e.g., from electricity generation and energy sourcing) compared to the radioactive emissions of U-235.
Land use	pt	Use and transformation of land for agriculture, roads, housing, mining or other purposes. The impacts can vary and include loss of species, organic matter content of soil, or soil itself (erosion). This is a composite indicator measuring impacts on four soil properties (biotic production, erosion resistance, groundwater regeneration and mechanical filtration), expressed in points (Pts).

Table A1. Cont.

Impact Category	Unit	Description
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq.	The potential impacts of all relevant substances on ozone depletion are converted to their equivalent of kilograms of trichlorofluoromethane (also called Freon-11 and R-11); hence, the unit of measurement is in kilograms of CFC-11 equivalent (kg CFC-11 eq).
Particulate matter	disease incidences	This indicator measures the adverse impacts on human health caused by emissions of Particulate Matter (PM) and its precursors (e.g., NO _x and SO ₂). The potential impact of PM is measured as the change in mortality due to PM emissions, expressed as disease incidence per kg of PM2.5 emitted.
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq.	The potential impact of substances contributing to photochemical ozone formation is converted into the equivalent of kilograms of Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds (e.g., alcohols and aromatics; kg NMVOC eq).
Resource use (fossils)	MJ	The basic idea behind this impact category is that extracting resources today will force future generations to extract less or different resources. The amount of materials contributing to resource use, fossils, are converted into MJ.
Resource use (minerals and metals)	kg Sb eq.	This impact category has the same underlying basic idea as the impact category “resource use, fossils”. The amount of materials contributing to resource depletion are converted into equivalents of kilograms of antimony (kg Sb eq).
Water use	m ³ water eq	The impact category considers the availability or scarcity of water in regions where the activity takes place. The potential impact is expressed in cubic meters (m ³) of water use related to the local scarcity of water.

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